

**PROSPECTS FOR OBTAINING LIQUID FUEL FROM POLYETHYLENE
WASTE VIA LOW-TEMPERATURE CATALYTIC PYROLYSIS**

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At present, plastic waste, particularly polyethylene (PE) waste, represents one of the major global environmental challenges. Due to its high chemical stability, polyethylene does not readily degrade under natural conditions and accumulates in the environment over long periods. Therefore, the recycling of polyethylene waste and the production of value-added products from it are of significant scientific and practical importance.

In recent years, extensive research has been conducted on the conversion of polyethylene into liquid fuels via catalytic pyrolysis. In particular, studies have been carried out to evaluate the efficiency of liquid fuel production from plastics using various iron-based catalysts. Three Fe/USY catalysts, namely Fe(O-550)/USY, Fe(R-300)/USY, and Fe(R-450)/USY, were prepared and their catalytic activities in polyethylene pyrolysis for liquid product formation were investigated. The results demonstrated that the yield of liquid fuel followed the order: Fe(O-550)/USY (72.5%) > Fe(R-300)/USY (69.9%) > Fe(R-450)/USY (66.7%). It was also established that the liquid fraction consisted of a mixture of hydrocarbons in the C₆–C₃₄ range. Catalysts prepared from pure iron metal exhibited higher activity compared to others and were particularly suitable for producing light and aromatic fractions during the catalytic pyrolysis of polyethylene [1].

The catalytic pyrolysis of polyethylene in the presence of iron catalysts has been studied in the temperature range of 300–500 °C in an inert nitrogen atmosphere within a closed reactor. It was observed that the presence of the catalyst lowers the decomposition temperature, and the highest yield of liquid products is obtained at 350–

400 °C. The liquid products mainly consist of aliphatic hydrocarbons, while the proportion of aromatic compounds increases with increasing temperature and residence time. At higher temperatures, secondary reactions intensify, leading to a decrease in liquid yield and an increase in gas formation. Wax-like products are formed at 300–350 °C, maximum liquid fuel yield is achieved at 350–400 °C, and gas formation becomes dominant at 450–500 °C [2].

It has been reported that the highest efficiency of polyethylene pyrolysis in the presence of an iron catalyst is achieved at 350 °C. Under these conditions, a liquid product yield of 80.88% relative to the initial polyethylene mass was obtained, while gas and solid residue yields were 17.24% and 1.88%, respectively. The liquid fraction consisted mainly of C₆–C₁₆ hydrocarbons, with paraffins accounting for 59.70% of the composition. The iron catalyst enhances carbon chain cracking and promotes paraffin formation. The resulting fuel products were rich in naphtha, petrol, and diesel fractions, and their physicochemical properties were found to comply with industrial fuel standards. Moreover, the iron catalyst minimised solid residues and enabled the production of high-quality liquid fuels [3].

In the present study, the possibility of conducting polyethylene waste pyrolysis at relatively low temperatures (300–310 °C) in the presence of an iron catalyst was investigated. In the experiment, polyethylene and iron powder were mixed in a mass ratio of 100:1 and heated in a closed reactor under conditions close to an inert atmosphere. The volatile products formed during the process were condensed, and the liquid fraction was collected.

According to the experimental results, the yield of liquid products reached 55–56% relative to the initial polyethylene mass. Although this value is lower than those reported in the literature at higher temperatures, the use of lower temperatures offers a significant advantage in terms of energy efficiency. This can be explained by the ability

of the iron catalyst to activate chain scission reactions even at relatively low temperatures.

The physical properties of the obtained liquid product were also examined. The density determined by the pycnometric method was 0.77 g/cm^3 at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is close to that of commercial petrol (AI-98). This indicates the potential applicability of the obtained product as a fuel. The light yellow colour and high flammability of the liquid product suggest the presence of light hydrocarbons. However, for a more comprehensive understanding of the process, further analysis of the chemical composition of the liquid fraction is required. This will enable a deeper insight into the reaction mechanism and a more accurate evaluation of product quality.

REFERENCES

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